

IMPACT OF PUBLIC SECTOR FRAUD ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Keywords: Fraud, Economics, Growth, Corruption and Inflation	Abstract: <i>This study investigates the effect of public sector fraud and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria over the period 2000–2024. An ex-post facto research design was adopted, relying entirely on secondary data sourced from the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC), Auditor-General’s reports, Transparency International, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and the World Bank. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis was employed to examine the relationship between public sector fraud, inflation, and economic growth, while diagnostic tests including unit root and multicollinearity assessments were conducted to ensure the robustness of results. Descriptive analysis revealed steady growth in GDP, substantial variability in fraud cases, and significant fluctuations in inflation during the study period. The regression results indicated that both fraud ($\beta = -0.1136$; $p = 0.1569$) and inflation ($\beta = -0.0099$; $p = 0.4442$) negatively affected economic growth, but their effects were statistically insignificant. The joint insignificance of the variables, as evidenced by the F-statistic ($p = 0.2067$), suggests that neither fraud nor inflation independently explains Nigeria’s growth trajectory. The findings imply that while public sector fraud and inflation are undesirable and negatively associated with growth, Nigeria’s economic performance is more</i>
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strongly influenced by broader structural and institutional factors such as oil dependency, governance quality, and fiscal management. The study concludes that strengthening anti-fraud institutions and adopting comprehensive macroeconomic reforms are necessary to mitigate the adverse effects of fraud and inflation while promoting sustainable economic growth.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Fraud in Nigeria’s public sector has emerged as a major socio-economic challenge, undermining economic growth, development, and public trust. It encompasses activities such as embezzlement, contract inflation, payroll fraud, and procurement irregularities, which divert critical resources from national development. Rooted in governance weaknesses and a culture of impunity, the problem intensified after Nigeria’s oil discovery, reinforcing the “resource curse” where resource revenues are misappropriated instead of supporting industrialization and infrastructure (Sala-i-Martin & Subramanian, 2013).

However, some empirical evidence confirms that corruption and fraud significantly reduce GDP growth by distorting resource allocation, discouraging investment, raising business costs, and weakening the effectiveness of public spending (Akinlabi & Okonkwo, 2021; Ajie & Wokekoro, 2012). Fraud undermines economic stability by widening fiscal deficits, increasing debt, and shrinking the tax base, while corruption scandals erode institutional trust and reduce tax compliance (Transparency International, 2024). The consequences extend

to poor service delivery, worsened poverty, rising inequality, and social unrest. In sectors like healthcare, diversion of funds hampers human capital development (Onwujekwe et al., 2019). Although anti-fraud institutions such as the EFCC and ICPC have made progress in prosecuting offenders and recovering funds, their effectiveness is weakened by political interference, limited resources, and legal loopholes (Olujobi, 2020). Reforms like the Whistle-Blowing Policy and digital governance tools (e.g., e-payments, biometric verification) show promise in curbing fraud (Federal Ministry of Finance, 2017). However, Nigeria still ranks poorly on global corruption indices, with the World Bank (2022) highlighting that effective anti-fraud measures require political will to hold powerful individuals accountable. The economic cost of fraud remains staggering, with billions of dollars lost annually that could otherwise support infrastructure, job creation, and poverty reduction (Umar & Ogbuagu, 2020). Overall, public sector fraud persists as a systemic barrier to Nigeria’s sustainable development and institutional credibility

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria’s economic growth has been persistently hampered by entrenched public sector fraud,

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manifested through embezzlement, contract inflation, procurement irregularities, ghost workers, and diversion of public funds. Despite the country's abundant natural and human resources, corruption has deprived it of vital resources, resulting in erratic and suboptimal economic performance (Ajie & Wokekoro, 2012; Sala-i-Martin & Subramanian, 2013).

Transparency International (2024) ranks Nigeria among the most corrupt nations globally, with corruption significantly weakening GDP growth by deterring investment, misallocating resources, and reducing the effectiveness of public spending (Akinlabi & Okonkwo, 2021). This has led to chronic underinvestment in infrastructure, healthcare, and education, fueling poverty and widening inequality. High-profile fraud cases in oil, public works, and healthcare sectors have further eroded public trust in institutions and weakened tax compliance (Umar & Ogbuagu, 2020).

Although anti-corruption bodies such as the EFCC and ICPC exist, their effectiveness is undermined by political interference, limited funding, and weak enforcement capacity (Olujobi, 2020). New measures, including the Whistle-Blowing Policy and digital financial management systems, have yielded some successes in fund recovery but have not significantly reduced the prevalence of fraud (Federal Ministry of Finance, 2017).

The persistence of fraud raises critical questions about its direct and indirect effects on Nigeria's economic development. Empirical inquiry is

necessary to identify the mechanisms such as reduced investment, inefficiencies, and lower productivity through which corruption undermines growth. Addressing fraud is therefore essential for achieving sustainable economic progress, advancing Nigeria's diversification agenda, and meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

1.3 Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to examine the relationship between public sector fraud and economic growth in Nigeria, with a view to determining the extent to which fraudulent practices within government institutions hinder the nation's economic performance. Specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of public sector fraud on economic growth in Nigeria
- ii. Determine contract inflation on economic growth in Nigeria

1.4 Research Questions

- i. What is the effect of public sector fraud on economic growth in Nigeria?
- iii. How does inflation affects economic growth in Nigeria?

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study investigates the role of public sector fraud as a critical barrier to Nigeria's economic growth, focusing on both its direct and indirect impacts. By providing empirical evidence on how fraudulent practices within government institutions undermine macroeconomic performance, the research bridges the gap between anecdotal accounts of corruption and

systematic measurement of its economic consequences.

The study's findings are expected to support policymakers in designing effective anti-fraud strategies, strengthening institutional capacity, and improving the efficiency of public spending. Insights generated can guide reforms that promote transparency, accountability, and the elimination of governance loopholes, while also assisting agencies such as the EFCC and ICPC in aligning their enforcement strategies with economic development objectives.

Beyond policy implications, the research contributes to the broader academic discourse on governance and economic performance in emerging economies. It provides a reference point for future studies on sector-specific or cross-country impacts of fraud. Ultimately, the study underscores the economic costs of corruption in Nigeria and highlights the need for targeted reforms to foster sustainable growth, reduce poverty, and achieve long-term development goals, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Conceptual Review

2.1 The Concept of Public Sector Fraud

Public sector fraud in Nigeria refers to deliberate acts of deception or misrepresentation by public officials or their associates to gain illicit financial or material benefits at the expense of the state and its citizens (Button et al., 2015). It manifests through embezzlement, payroll fraud, contract inflation, procurement abuses, and diversion of

resources, often enabled by weak institutional frameworks, poor enforcement of anti-corruption laws, and political interference (Owolabi, 2020; Adebayo & Ojo, 2022).

Fraud undermines economic growth, defined as the sustained increase in a nation's productive capacity measured by real GDP (Todaro & Smith, 2020), by diverting scarce resources from developmental projects to private interests. Institutional economics theory emphasizes that the quality of institutions critically shapes economic outcomes (North, 1990). Fraud depletes government revenue, disrupts budgetary allocations, and reduces investment in vital sectors such as infrastructure, health, and education (Mauro, 1995; Tanzi & Davoodi, 1998). The impact in Nigeria is evident in poor infrastructure, unemployment, weak productivity, and underfunded social services, despite significant oil revenues (Egwemi, 2013). Fraud also deters domestic and foreign investment by raising business risks, leading to economic stagnation, poverty, and inequality (Transparency International, 2023). Channels of impact include inflated project costs (Rose-Ackerman, 1999), reduced tax compliance (Alm & Torgler, 2011), fiscal instability (Okonjo-Iweala, 2018), and brain drain as skilled workers migrate (Uzonwanne, 2015).

Although Nigeria has established institutions such as the EFCC, ICPC, and the Whistle-Blowing Policy, recurring high-profile fraud cases and persistent low rankings on corruption indices suggest limited success (Transparency

International, 2023). Within corruption debates, while some argue fraud may “grease the wheels” by bypassing bureaucratic hurdles (Leff, 1964), Nigerian evidence strongly supports the “sand the wheels” perspective, showing that fraud erodes efficiency, equity, and long-term economic sustainability (Mauro, 1995; Adebayo & Ojo, 2022).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Principal Agent Theory

The principal-agent framework offers a fundamental theory for comprehending fraud in the public sector. Elected officials or citizens (principals) delegate authority to public servants or bureaucrats (agents); however, information asymmetries and inadequate oversight enable agents to pursue their own interests instead of those of the principals, potentially leading to embezzlement, procurement fraud, or ghost-worker schemes. The principal-agent model elucidates how inadequate supervision, suboptimal incentive frameworks, and diminished responsibility rationalise agents' diversion of public resources, resulting in fiscal leakages and diminished public service provision that ultimately impede growth. This theoretical framework is extensively employed in corruption research to illustrate the significance of institutional design and oversight in mitigating fraud.

2.2.2 Theory of Rent-Seeking

The Rent Seeking Theory and public-choice views enhance the principal-agent explanation by illustrating how people and groups allocate

resources to obtain unmerited benefits from public office or policy discretion. Rent-seeking transpires when individuals or entities engage in lobbying, bribery, or manipulation of procurement and licensing procedures to capture economic rents, resulting in allocative inefficiency; resources are diverted from the production of goods and services to get preferential transfers. The cumulative impact of rent-seeking results in diminished aggregate productivity and decelerated economic growth, as productive investment is supplanted by zero-sum transfers, leading to a significant decline in the social returns on public expenditure. These insights elucidate why economies plagued by widespread public sector fraud experience persistent capital misallocation and hindered development.

2.3 Empirical Review

Chima and Obiah (2021) explored the 21st-century public sector accounting framework as a tool for strengthening governance and accountability in developing nations. Using a quasi-experimental design and data collected from 300 directors, accountants, and auditors in ministries, departments, and agencies (MDAs), the study employed Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Chi-square for analysis. Findings revealed a significant correlation between the adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) and improvements in public sector management and accountability.

Similarly, Wahidahwati and Asyik (2022) examined the role of auditor characteristics experience, ethics, professional scepticism, and personality type in fraud detection within public sector audits in East Java, Indonesia. Based on a sample of 156 audit personnel and analyzed using multiple regression, the study established that these auditor attributes have a positive and significant effect on fraud detection, thereby highlighting the importance of professional competence and ethical standards in enhancing transparency and accountability in public entities.

Complementing these perspectives, James and Ibanichuka (2014) investigated fraud prevention and financial control challenges in the Nigerian banking sector. Their findings confirmed that strong internal financial controls are positively linked to fraud prevention. The study emphasized the necessity for compliance with prudential guidelines, sound recruitment practices, and effective management oversight to minimize fraud risks, noting that human error and weak institutional commitment often undermine control systems.

Collectively, these studies underscore the critical role of robust accounting frameworks, auditor competence, and strong financial controls in fostering accountability, detecting fraud, and improving governance in both public and financial sectors.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design because it seeks to examine the relationship between public sector fraud and economic growth using existing secondary data without manipulating the variables under investigation. The *ex-post facto* approach is appropriate since both public sector fraud and economic growth are historical phenomena whose data can be obtained from official government records, anti-corruption agencies, and international databases (Kerlinger & Lee, 2000).

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study covered Nigeria's public sector fraud records and economic performance indicators over a defined period, proposed as 2000–2024. This period is selected to capture various democratic administrations, institutional reforms, and anti-corruption policy implementations, allowing for a more robust trend analysis.

3.3 Sample size and Sample Technique

The sample will be determined by the availability and reliability of data within this time frame. Public sector fraud will be proxied using indicators such as the total value of fraud cases reported by the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC), and relevant Auditor-General's reports, as well as the Transparency International Corruption Perception Index (CPI) scores for Nigeria. Economic growth will be measured using the annual growth rate of Gross Domestic Product

(GDP) sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI).

3.4 Data Collection

Data collection will rely entirely on secondary sources. Fraud-related data will be obtained from EFCC and ICPC annual reports, official audit publications, and international governance datasets. Economic growth figures will be retrieved from NBS publications, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletins, and the World Bank database. These sources are chosen for their credibility, accessibility, and consistency over time.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The method of data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarise the trends and patterns in public sector fraud cases and economic growth rates over the study period. Inferential analysis will employ the **Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model** to determine the extent and direction of the relationship between public sector fraud (independent variable) and economic growth (dependent variable). The regression model will take the following form:

$$GDPT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FRAUDt + \beta_2 X_t + \mu_t$$

Where:

GDPT = Economic growth rate in year t

FRAUDt = Measured indicator of public sector fraud in year t

X_t = Control variables such as inflation rate, foreign direct investment inflows, and government expenditure

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2$ = Model parameters

μ_t = Error term

Diagnostic tests such as the unit root test (Augmented Dickey-Fuller) and **co-integration** test (Johansen) will be conducted to ensure the time series data are stationary and that a long-run equilibrium relationship exists between the variables. The model will also be tested for multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and autocorrelation to ensure robustness of results.

3.6 Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations addressed by ensuring that all secondary data sources are properly cited, and that the study avoids data manipulation or misrepresentation. Since the research uses publicly available data, no personal or confidential information will be disclosed. This methodological approach is expected to provide empirical evidence on how public sector fraud influences Nigeria's economic growth trajectory, offering a basis for policy recommendations aimed at reducing fraud and fostering sustainable development.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The data collected are presented, analyzed and interpreted in this chapter. The hypotheses for the study are tested as well as discussion of findings. The data are presented in tables and

analyzed. The hypotheses are tested using multiple linear regression method.

4.1 Data Presentation

The data captured for this study include Gross domestic products (dependent variable); and financial fraud and inflation rate (independent variables) for the period under review.

The data is presented in the appendix.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics helps to explain and summarize the data used for the study. The descriptive statistics used in this study include mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	GDP	FIN. FRAUD	INFLATION
Mean	53887777	12636.04	13.81440
Median	58180350	9383.670	12.54000
Maximum	77936100	53522.86	37.29000
Minimum	18480670	902.0968	5.390000
Std. Dev.	18251198	13714.01	6.449881
Skewness	-0.402264	1.817829	2.035554
Kurtosis	1.793088	5.375481	8.263214
Jarque-Bera	2.191565	19.64678	46.12014
Probability	0.334278	0.000054	0.000000
Sum	1.3509	315901.0	345.3600
Sum Sq. Dev.	7.9915	4.5109	998.4232
Observations	25	25	25

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025 (E-views Output)

The results in Table 4.1 showed that GDP has a mean value of ₦53,887,777 million, with a minimum of ₦18,480,670 million and a maximum of ₦77,936,100 million. This indicates steady growth in GDP during the study period. The standard deviation (₦18,251,198 million) reflects moderate dispersion, while the skewness value (-0.402) indicates a slight left-skewed

distribution. The kurtosis (1.793) is less than 3, suggesting a relatively flat (platykurtic) distribution. The Jarque-Bera probability (0.334) is above 0.05, implying that GDP is normally distributed.

For Financial Fraud, the mean value is ₦12,636.04 million, with a minimum of ₦902.10 million and a maximum of ₦53,522.86 million.

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The high standard deviation (₦13,714.01 million) relative to the mean indicates substantial variability in fraud cases over the years. The skewness (1.818) and kurtosis (5.375) suggest a right-skewed and leptokurtic distribution, reflecting that a few extreme fraud cases drive the distribution. The Jarque-Bera probability (0.000054) indicates that financial fraud is not normally distributed.

Inflation has a mean rate of 13.81%, with values ranging from a minimum of 5.39% to a maximum of 37.29%. The standard deviation (6.45) showed moderate fluctuations in inflation. The skewness (2.036) and kurtosis (8.263) reveal a strongly right-skewed and leptokurtic distribution, indicating the presence of extreme inflationary episodes. The Jarque-Bera probability (0.0000) confirms that inflation is not normally distributed.

4.3 Unit Root Test

Table 4.2 Intermediate ADF test results UNTITLED

Series	Prob.	Lag	Max Lag	Obs
GDP	0.4601	0	4	24
FIN. FRAUD	0.0062	1	4	23
INFLATION	0.9805	0	4	24

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025 (E-views Output)

From table 4.2, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is used to check whether the time series is stationary or non-stationary. The result in the table showed the existence of stationarity for financial fraud because its probability values are less than 5% level of significance.

The results also showed that the time series data for GDP and inflation indicate non-stationarity ($p > 0.05$), implying that their mean, variance and autocorrelation structure changes over time.

4.4 Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity occurs when two or more explanatory variables in a regression model are highly correlated, making it difficult to isolate their individual effects on the dependent variable. Severe multicollinearity inflates the

standard errors of coefficients, weakens statistical significance, and can lead to unstable estimates.

To detect multicollinearity, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is commonly employed. The VIF measures how much the variance of an estimated regression coefficient is increased because of collinearity. According to the rule of thumb, a VIF value of 1 indicates no correlation, values between 1 and 5 suggest moderate correlation that is not problematic, while values above 10 signal serious multicollinearity.

In this study, the VIF results show that all explanatory variables (fraud and inflation) have centered VIF values of approximately 1.05, which are far below the critical threshold of 10. This

implies that there is no evidence of multicollinearity among the independent variables in the model. Consequently, the regression estimates can be considered reliable and stable

Table 4.3 Variance Inflation Factors

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
FRAUD	0.006005	79.71510	1.046763
INFLATION	0.000160	6.048696	1.046763
C	0.466118	76.28481	NA

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025 (E-views Output)

4.5 Test of Hypotheses

The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis of no significant association if the probability value is less than 5% and accept the alternative.

Table 4.4 Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FRAUD	-0.113586	0.077492	-1.465772	0.1569
INFLATION	-0.009859	0.012655	-0.779082	0.4442
C	18.88617	0.682728	27.66279	0.0000
R-squared	0.133504	Mean dependent var	17.73373	
Adjusted R-squared	0.054732	S.D. dependent var	0.401996	
S.E. of regression	0.390840	Akaike info criterion	1.071129	
Sum squared resid	3.360628	Schwarz criterion	1.217394	
Log likelihood	-10.38911	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.111697	
F-statistic	1.694809	Durbin-Watson stat	0.581184	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.206743			

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025 (E-views Output)

Test of Hypothesis One

Public sector fraud has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria

The regression result in Table 4.4 showed that the coefficient of fraud is -0.1136 with a *t-statistic* of -1.466 and a probability value of 0.1569 . Since the p-value is greater than the 5%

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significance level, the effect of public sector fraud on economic growth is statistically insignificant. Given this outcome, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted. This implies that public sector fraud does not have a statistically significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria within the period under study.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Inflation has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria

The regression result in Table 4.4 showed that the coefficient of inflation was -0.0009859 with a *t-statistic* of -0.779082 and a probability value of 0.4442 . Since the *p*-value is greater than the 5% significance level, the effect of inflation on economic growth is statistically insignificant. Given this outcome, the null hypothesis (H_0) two is accepted. This implies that inflation does not have a statistically significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria within the period under study.

4.6 Discussion of the Findings

The study investigated the effect of public sector fraud and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria using regression analysis. The findings revealed that both fraud and inflation exhibited negative coefficients, indicating an inverse relationship with economic growth. However, their effects were found to be statistically insignificant within the study period.

Specifically, the coefficient of fraud was -0.1136 with a probability value of 0.1569 , suggesting that public sector fraud does not exert a significant influence on economic growth in Nigeria. This finding is in contrasts with studies

such as Wahidahwati and Asyik (2022), which established that corruption and fraud significantly reduce economic growth by distorting resource allocation. The insignificance in this study may suggest that fraud, though prevalent, operates alongside stronger macroeconomic variables that overshadow its direct effect on growth.

Similarly, inflation recorded a coefficient of -0.0099 with a probability value of 0.4442 , indicating a negative but insignificant relationship with economic growth. This implies that inflationary pressures during the study period did not significantly alter the trajectory of Nigeria's economic growth. This result is inconsistent with findings by James and Ibanichuka (2014), They found a positive correlation between financial control implementation and fraud prevention, and they suggested that banks adhere to prudential norms and other internal control policies. In the Nigerian context, the result may be explained by structural challenges, policy inconsistencies, and the resilience of informal economic activities that buffer the economy from short-term inflationary shocks.

The joint effect of fraud and inflation on economic growth, as shown by the *F*-statistic (1.6948 , $p = 0.2067$), was also not statistically significant. This means that the explanatory variables, when combined, do not meaningfully explain variations in economic growth in Nigeria within the period under review. Furthermore, the relatively low *R*-squared value (0.134)

suggests that only 13.4% of the variations in economic growth are explained by fraud and inflation, while the remaining 86.6% is attributable to other macroeconomic and institutional factors not captured in the model. Overall, the findings indicate that while fraud and inflation negatively relate to growth, their statistical insignificance suggests that Nigeria's economic growth is more strongly influenced by other structural and policy-related factors such as public investment, external debt, oil price fluctuations, and governance quality. This underscores the need for a holistic policy approach that addresses not only fraud and inflation but also the broader macroeconomic and institutional environment to achieve sustainable growth.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This last chapter presents a summary of the research, conclusion and recommendations. It also discussed arrears of opportunity for further research and contribution to existing body of knowledge.

5.1 Summary of the findings

Ex-post-facto research design was adopted for the study. The data for the study were obtained from secondary source for the period of twenty-five years (2000 to 2024). Ordinary least square regression, with the aid of E-Views, was used in analysing the data and testing the stated hypotheses. It was revealed that financial fraud and inflation have a negative and insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria

5.2 Conclusion

The study set out to examine the effect of public sector fraud and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria. The empirical findings indicate that both variables have a negative but statistically insignificant effect on economic growth during the study period. Specifically, fraud, though inversely related to growth, did not show a significant impact, suggesting that while fraudulent practices may erode institutional trust and efficiency, their direct effect on growth may be overshadowed by other macroeconomic and structural factors. Similarly, inflation was found to negatively influence growth, but the insignificance of its effect reflects the resilience of the Nigerian economy to short-term price shocks, possibly due to the dominance of the informal sector and the influence of external economic drivers.

The joint insignificance of fraud and inflation, as revealed by the F-statistic, further suggests that these variables do not meaningfully explain variations in Nigeria's economic growth within the study period. The low explanatory power of the model reinforces the notion that other macroeconomic variables such as investment, oil revenues, government expenditure, exchange rate dynamics, and governance quality play a more dominant role in shaping economic growth outcomes. In summary, the findings conclude that while public sector fraud and inflation are undesirable and negatively associated with growth, they do not independently exert a statistically significant influence on Nigeria's

economic growth during the period under review. This highlights the complexity of the growth process in Nigeria, where structural, institutional, and policy-related factors interact to determine economic outcomes.

5.3 Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should strengthen anti-fraud agencies such as the EFCC and ICPC, providing them with adequate resources and autonomy to prevent, detect, and prosecute fraudulent practices in the public sector.
2. The Central Bank of Nigeria should implement inflation-targeting policies and coordinate effectively with fiscal authorities

to stabilize prices while promoting investment and productivity growth.

5.4 Policy Implications of the Findings

1. The insignificant effect of fraud on economic growth implies that while fraud is harmful, its impact may be indirect, operating through weakened institutions and reduced public trust in governance rather than immediate growth outcomes.

2. The insignificant impact of inflation suggests that growth in Nigeria is driven more by structural and external factors (e.g., oil dependency, fiscal management, exchange rate volatility). Thus, inflation control policies must be complemented with structural reforms to achieve sustainable growth.

Appendix

YEAR	FIN. FRAUD (N'M)	INFLATION (%)	GDP (N'M)
2000	2,857.11	6.93	25,430,402.00
2001	11,243.94	11.87	26,935,320.00
2002	12,919.55	12.88	31,064,270.00
2003	9,383.67	14.03	33,346,620.00
2004	11,754.00	15.00	36,431,370.00
2005	10,606.18	17.86	38,777,010.00

2006	4,832.17	8.23	41,126,680.00
2007	10,005.81	5.39	43,837,390.00
2008	53,522.86	11.58	46,802,760.00
2009	41,265.50	12.54	50,564,260.00
2010	902.10	13.74	55,469,350.00
2011	1,881.90	10.83	58,180,350.00
2012	17,965.00	12.22	60,670,050.00
2013	21,795.00	8.50	63,942,850.00
2014	7,750.15	8.05	67,977,460.00
2015	4,374.51	9.01	69,780,690.00
2016	2,396.00	15.70	68,652,430.00
2017	2,372.00	16.50	69,205,690.00
2018	15,151.00	12.10	70,536,350.00
2019	5,464.00	11.40	72,094,090.00
2020	5,334.00	13.25	70,800,540.00
2021	1,447.35	16.95	73,382,770.00

2022	6,753.57	18.85	75,768,950.00
2023	11,274.70	24.66	77,936,100.00
2024	42,648.95	37.29	18,480,670.00

Source: NDIC Annual Reports and CBN Statistical Bulletins

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